

Momentum Viewpoint of Quantum Bound State Part II

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In Part I, we argued that quantum mechanics (at least the $\exp(ipx)$ feature of it) is a statistical tallying approach which uses a probability $\exp(ipx)$ which ensures conservation of momentum. As a result, we argued that one describes a bound state by the set of possible p values (both p and $-p$ at different times because time does not matter in an average over time scheme), their $\exp(ipx)$ s and integrals $W^* W dx$ and $\text{Integral } W^* \text{ operator } W dx$ where $W(x) = \sum \text{over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ such that $P(p)=a^*(p)a(p)$.

In this note, we ask: How can such a tallying scheme match Newtonian physics for a bound state, which is observed in nature? We first suggest that the $\exp(ipx)$ probability approach is more general than Newtonian mechanics because $\exp(ipx)$ suggests a wavelength \hbar/p . If this wavelength, however, is tiny compared to the system length, then one may associate p with a very small dx which matches Newtonian mechanics. As a result, a Newtonian bound state has a set of p values (actually $-p/+p$ pairs) (which have sharp resolution from $a(p)$), each with their unique x point and different probabilities proportional to dt , the time spent in a little dx . As long as the quantum result matches this probability description, then the two are compatible. We note that the crests and troughs of quantum mechanics are due to the $\exp(ipx)$ periodicity nature needed for conservation of momentum, but this is an extra feature of quantum mechanics. Classical mechanics, we argue, is less precise and does not make use of these crests and troughs.

As a result, we try to argue that the $a^*(p)a(p)=P(p)$ quantum values together with p mapping to a precise x is compatible with high energy quantum results. We consider the quantum oscillator as an example.

Classical and Quantum Mechanics

Classical mechanics follows a particle in time and space. The particle has a velocity at x in dx and $v+dv$ at $x+dx$ because a force acts on it in dx . Momentum is conserved in classical physics, but this conservation holds in dx which is a tiny region tending to 0.

We argued in previous notes (see Part I for reference) that one may create a probability type function $\exp(ipx)$ which allows for conservation of momentum, a fundamental principle in classical physics. This conservation occurs through:

$$\text{Integral } \exp(-ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x) dx = 0 \text{ if } p_1 \neq p_2 \quad ((1))$$

The integral need not range over all space, but given a natural length in the problem $\hbar/(p_1-p_2)$, this suffices for a length and it may not be very small compared to the system length. If it is, however, then one has a classical situation in which conservation of momentum occurs pretty much in a dx which is tiny compared to the system length. Such a wavelength does not occur in classical mechanics and so we argue that quantum mechanics is more general.

Tallying Mechanism

We suggested in Part I that quantum mechanics is a statistical tallying approach. We argued that for a bound state, one makes a list of the possible p values (all of them) together with $\exp(ipx)$ for each to have momentum conservation and pieces of operator expectation values. We noted that not only does one use ((1)), or $\int W^*(x)W(x)dx$ for $W(x)=\sum$ over p $a(p)\exp(ipx)$, but one may extend this to:

$$\int W^* \text{ operator } W dx \quad ((2))$$

In such a case, one checks if Operator $W(x)$ makes allowable transitions (momentum conserving ones) to W^* .

These ideas lead to the time-independent Schrodinger equation in the form:

$$\int dx W^*(x) \left[\frac{1}{2m} \hbar^2 (-id/dx) (-id/dx) W + \int W^* V(x)W \right] = E \int dx W^* W \quad ((3))$$

As a result, the tallying done for a quantum bound state is to list the allowable p values and associated $\exp(ipx)$, $a^*(p)a(p)$ $pp/2m$ and $a(p) \sum$ over k $V_k a(p-k)$ with each (see Part I). This is the statistical approach. It is irrelevant that $-p$ and p may actually occur at different times (as they do in a classical problem) in a statistical approach.

The question then becomes: For high energy levels, does the quantum tallying approach map into some approach available for classical mechanics? (We note that ((3)) may be converted into a differential equation which is an eigenvalue one (and with $W(x)$ tending to 0 at \pm infinite, one has discrete E values.)

Classical Mechanics written as Tallying Scheme

If one considers a classical bound state, one may write all \pm p pairs and their corresponding x values. We consider the oscillator as an example. A \pm p pair corresponds to a unique x and the energy there is:

$$pp/2m + .5kxx = E \quad ((4))$$

Furthermore, there is a probability associated with time proportional to δt (1).

Thus, it seems that one may describe the classical oscillator in a scheme which is very similar to that of the quantum mechanical oscillator with the exception of the crests and troughs of quantum mechanics and the lack of p and x resolution (linked to the crest and trough widths in $W(x)$ and $a(p)$).

We argue that quantum mechanics is more general theory than classical mechanics and that the crests and troughs are part of this generalization. The crest-troughs allow one to solve 2-slit interference and one dimensional reflection-refraction which do not follow from classical mechanics. Thus, we argue that one does not have to worry about the crests-troughs at high E , except for the fact that p and x resolution is very high. In other words one knows exact p and x values so ((4)) should hold. One may also note that $P(p)=a^*(p)a(p)$, i.e. there is a probability for different p values, but we have argued that each x classically (which is associated with a unique $-/+p$ pair for the oscillator) has a probability proportional to δt . This should also hold for the envelope of $W^*(x)W(x)$ as argued in (1).

Classically, one has a set of p values and not all are allowed, i.e. $p_{max} p_{max}/2m = E$. The Hermite polynomials multiplied by $\exp(-.5\sqrt{km} xx)$ for $W(x)$ mean that $a(p)$ has the same math form, but with a different constant. Thus, one may see that $W^*(x)W(x)$ drops off at the classical turning points for high energy and there is also a drop-off for p , presumably at the p values which satisfy $pp/2m = E$.

As a result, it seems that one may describe a classical bound system in terms of $+/-p$ pairs, their unique x values and a probability proportional to time.

We argue that if one ignores the crest-troughs of high E quantum oscillator solutions, then there is both spatial and momentum cutoff and very high p and x resolution suggesting exact p and x values which satisfy $pp/2m + .5kxx=E$. The probability $a^*(p)a(p)$ could also be considered proportional to δp because there is a unique $-/+ p$ pair at each x and the envelope of $W^*(x)W(x)$ is proportional to δt according to (1).

Thus, the high energy quantum and classical pictures coincide, but only if one writes the classical scheme in a probabilistic manner, i.e. $\{ p, x, \delta t \}$. These points, however, can be converted into the deterministic $x(t)$ picture. We suggest that this is the manner in which high energy quantum mechanics maps into classical mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue quantum mechanics is a statistical theory based on $\exp(ipx)$, a math probability-type function which ensures conservation of momentum. Given that a characteristic length \hbar/p appears, we suggest that this theory is more general than classical mechanics. This is the case because quantum mechanics describes 2-slit interference and one dimensional reflection-refraction and classical mechanics does not.

We argued in Part I that a bound state is described quantum mechanically by listing all possible p values, giving the weights $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and considering, $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ with $\text{Integral } W^*(x)W(x)dx$ and $\text{Integral } W^*(x)$ operator $W(x)$. These integrals ensure conservation of momentum, but one does not need to integrate over all space. For example, $\text{Integral } dx \exp(-ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)$ is orthogonal in $\hbar/(p_2-p_1)$.

Classical physics follows a bound particle in time and certainly describes bound macroscopic states, such as an oscillator state. The question then is: How does quantum mechanics map to classical mechanics? We suggest that one requires \hbar/p to be very small. In such a case, momentum conservation and impulse hits occur in a tiny region, i.e. at an x point. In such a

case, one knows the p value needed at x , namely $p^2/2m + .5kx^2 = E$ for an oscillator. Both $W_n(x)$ and $a_n(p)$ have very high x and p resolution for high n (energy value). The fact that one still has $\exp(ipx)$ and crests and troughs is not an issue. These are features associated with momentum conservation. The point is that each $\pm p$ pair maps to a specific x which can be resolved and satisfies $p^2/2m + .5kx^2 = E_n$. The probability $a^*(p)a(p)$ should be proportional to Δx .

If one considers the oscillator quantum wavefunction, $W(x) = C \exp(-.5\sqrt{km} x^2)$ Hermite polynomial and the same math form for $a(p)$, then for high n , there is sharp p and x resolution, but also sharp drop-offs at classical cutoff points. Thus, the description of an oscillator system in terms of p and probability values still holds because one can find the x corresponding to p by using $p^2/2m + .5kx^2 = E$.

The quantum tallying approach matches the classical $\pm p$, x , probability proportional to Δx scheme with $p^2/2m + .5kx^2 = E$. From this one can create $x(t)$ which is the usual way in which one views classical mechanics. It does not seem to be at odds with quantum mechanics if one uses an envelope and removes crests and troughs in $W(x)$, $a(p)$, but at the same time notes that x and p resolutions are very high, i.e. pretty much at classical point values.

References

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